

Protocol for an Observational Study on the Effects of ADHD in Youth on Physical Activity

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Abstract

Background: Exercise is crucial to maintaining one’s well being and has been shown to help manage the symptoms of ADHD. Sports participation in particular could be an appealing form of physical activity for youth, as sports can make exercise more enjoyable. Given the importance of exercise on the lives of youth, we seek to examine the effect of ADHD on youth engagement in physical activity and sports.

Methods and Analysis: We propose a retrospective observational study comparing 647 youth with ADHD with 647 youth without ADHD. The primary outcome is frequency of physical activity. We utilize matching followed by regression-based covariance adjustment to control for potential confounders. We will also analyze the secondary outcome of youth sports participation, and plan to conduct subgroup analyses, stratified by sex and by age group, for both outcomes of interest.

Keywords: Observational study, pre-analysis plan, matching, causal inference

1 Background and Motivation

Exercise is a critical aspect of daily life and in maintaining one’s well being, and has been shown to have positive effects in treating the symptoms of Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) (Mehren et al., 2020). However, limited research has examined the association between ADHD in youth and physical activity. Given the interest in engaging youth with ADHD in physical activity to help manage symptoms, it is important to understand whether having ADHD is itself a barrier to participation in sports and exercise that would need to be overcome for successful uptake.

Previous observational studies have found that children and adolescents with ADHD were less likely to engage in physical activity (Cook et al., 2015; Kim et al., 2011; Mercurio et al., 2021); however, these studies controlled for only a limited number of covariates, mainly age, sex, race, and a measure of socioeconomic status. Other key covariates that may confound the association between ADHD and physical activity could have driven previous findings and therefore must be considered. For example, ADHD is highly comorbid with asthma (Cortese et al., 2018), autism (Zablotsky et al., 2020), and anxiety (Danielson et al., 2018), all of which may decrease one’s propensity or ability to engage in physical activity. Key structural barriers to participating in sports or outdoor physical activity, such as neighborhood safety (Lewis et al., 2015), are also inequitably experienced by youth with ADHD and should be considered. Thus, a wide range of potential confounders must be appropriately adjusted in order to confidently isolate the association between ADHD per se and physical activity.

In addition, it may be particularly useful to understand the propensity for youth with ADHD to participate in sports specifically. Sports are a form of physical activity that could be leveraged as a natural intervention for youth with ADHD, because they tend to make exercise more enjoyable (Henderson et al., 1999). Moreover, parents often perceive benefits of organized sports for their children and teens with ADHD because it provides athletes with structure, routine, and reinforcement of on-task behavior (Best, 2010; Pagani et al., 2020), key therapeutic strategies for ADHD (Chacko et al., 2016). These features make sports a particularly appealing physical activity intervention for youth with ADHD. However, very little work has examined the association between ADHD and sports participation, limiting our understanding of how likely youth with ADHD are to engage in sports.

In this observational study, we use more recent data from the 2022 National Health Interview Survey (NHIS), a nationally representative sample of U.S. children aged 0 – 17. A key benefit of the NHIS is its inclusion of a large number of baseline covariates, such as variables related to demographics, physical health, socioeconomic status, parental background, mental conditions, and neighborhood safety. Our primary focus will be on the effect of ADHD on youth physical activity. We will also study the effect of ADHD on the secondary outcome of sports participation.

To estimate the effect of ADHD on physical activity and sports participation, we utilize a matching approach to adjust for baseline variables; specifically, we use a pair match protocol that matches one treated individual (ADHD) to one control individual (non-ADHD). This matching procedure allows us to balance baseline covariates to infer the treatment effect of ADHD on the primary and secondary outcomes.

2 Eligibility and Exclusion Criteria

We only consider children aged 6 – 17, because no data on physical activity or sports participation was collected for subjects aged 0 – 5. The 2022 NHIS

contains 7464 subjects in total, of which 5073 were in the desired age range. We excluded 15 individuals who lacked information regarding ever having ADHD, so our sample of “treated” subjects consists of children who have ever had ADHD (663), and our sample of control subjects consists of children who have never had ADHD (4395). We also exclude 129 individuals lacking measurements the primary outcome of physical activity, 11 with ADHD and 118 without ADHD. Finally, we exclude 4 individuals who did not have information regarding the secondary outcome of sports participation, 1 with ADHD and 3 without ADHD.

Our final sample consists of 4925 subjects, containing 651 children with ADHD and 4274 children without ADHD.

3 Matching

We consider the covariates listed in Table 1. Due to low numbers, we exclude subjects missing data on sex (1), difficulty seeing (1), and anxiety (5).

Type	Covariate
Demographic Data	Sex Age Race
Physical Health	Ever had asthma Difficulty seeing Difficulty hearing sounds
Socioeconomic Status	Problems paying medical bills, past 12m Lifetime of lacking basic needs Income from public assistance Sample child family poverty ratio Receive food stamps, past 12m Worry food would run out
Parental Background	Count of all residential parents of the sample child Highest level of education of all SC’s parents
Other Mental Conditions	Ever had autism How often seems anxious, nervous, or worried How often seems sad or depressed
Neighborhood Safety	Traffic causes safety issues Crime causes safety issues

Table 1: List of covariates used in the pair matching procedure. Note that SC refers to the sample child.

To construct matched sets, we first estimate the propensity score, the conditional probability of having received treatment given a set of covariates, using the above covariates and indicators for missingness.

We then construct a distance matrix based on the rank-based Mahalanobis

distance, and match based on this distance matrix. We utilize a propensity score caliper as recommended by [Hansen \(2011\)](#), which causes a slight decrease in sample size by 4 treated individuals and 8 control individuals. This caliper prohibits matching individuals with very different propensity scores; consequently, some treated individuals have propensity scores that are too extreme in comparison to the control group, and they are unable to be matched. Similarly, some control individuals have propensity scores that are too extreme in comparison to the treatment group, so these individuals cannot be matched either. Therefore, we must remove these individuals that lack overlap with the opposite group.

We match one treated individual to one control individual. We match exactly for sex, meaning that boys are matched with boys and girls are matched with girls. Additionally, we also match exactly for age group (stratified by children (aged 6 – 12) and adolescents (aged 13 – 17)), meaning that children are matched with children and adolescents are matched with adolescents. Furthermore, because the covariate “Worry food would run out” is particularly difficult to balance, we introduce a small penalty to mismatches on this covariate, giving a slightly greater priority to balancing this covariate. The covariate balance prior to and after matching is given in [Table 2](#).

Covariate	Mean			Standardized Difference	
	T	C Before	C After	Before	After
Sex, Male, %	65.38	49.43	65.38	0.33	0.00
Age	12.58	11.73	12.52	0.25	0.02
Race, %					
Hispanic	19.01	26.97	16.69	-0.19	0.06
Non-Hispanic White only	63.06	47.97	71.87	0.31	-0.18
Non-Hispanic Black/African American only	9.43	10.41	6.03	-0.03	0.11
Non-Hispanic Asian only	1.85	8.23	1.39	-0.29	0.02
Non-Hispanic AIAN only	0.77	0.75	0.77	0.00	0.00
Non-Hispanic AIAN and any other group	0.77	0.94	0.15	-0.02	0.07
Other single and multiple races	5.10	4.73	3.09	0.02	0.09
Ever had asthma, %	20.56	11.74	17.00	0.24	0.10
Difficulty seeing, %					
No difficulty	93.20	95.01	96.91	-0.08	-0.16
Some difficulty	5.87	4.64	2.78	0.05	0.14
A lot of difficulty / Cannot do at all	0.93	0.35	0.31	0.09	0.07
Difficulty hearing sounds, %					
No difficulty	96.14	97.96	98.45	-0.11	-0.14
Some difficulty	3.55	1.87	1.39	0.10	0.13
A lot of difficulty	0.31	0.16	0.15	0.03	0.03
Problems paying medical bills, past 12m, %	16.23	10.71	10.97	0.16	0.15
Lifetime of lacking basic needs, %	7.26	3.52	4.48	0.16	0.12
Income from public assistance, %	5.87	4.78	4.17	0.05	0.08
Sample child family poverty ratio	3.77	3.97	3.98	-0.07	-0.07
Receive food stamps, past 12m, %	23.96	17.51	19.47	0.16	0.11
Worry food would run out, %					
Often true	6.18	3.35	3.71	0.14	0.11
Sometimes true	12.52	9.70	9.43	0.09	0.10
Never true	80.06	85.61	86.24	-0.15	-0.16
Count of all residential parents of the sample child	1.50	1.65	1.58	-0.27	-0.15
Highest level of education of all SC's parents, %					
Less than High School	4.48	6.00	3.25	-0.06	0.06
High School Graduate or equivalent	17.62	18.47	16.07	-0.02	0.04
Some college, no degree	11.28	11.34	12.21	0.00	-0.03
Associate degree	14.53	12.28	12.21	0.06	0.07
Bachelor's degree	23.49	25.29	27.36	-0.04	-0.09
Master's degree	15.92	17.55	18.24	-0.05	-0.06
Professional School or Doctoral degree	6.49	6.63	6.49	-0.01	0.00
Ever had autism, %	14.37	2.11	9.27	0.47	0.19
How often seems anxious, nervous, or worried, %					
Daily	19.32	4.52	18.08	0.48	0.04
Weekly	25.35	11.62	26.28	0.36	-0.02
Monthly	14.68	10.97	14.68	0.11	0.00
A few times a year	21.02	26.29	22.10	-0.13	-0.03
Never	19.63	46.59	18.86	-0.60	0.02
How often seems sad or depressed, %					
Daily	2.94	1.22	1.85	0.13	0.07
Weekly	10.20	4.87	9.43	0.21	0.03
Monthly	15.30	6.42	12.67	0.29	0.09
A few times a year	27.20	20.58	28.90	0.16	-0.04
Never	43.89	66.77	46.83	-0.48	-0.06
Traffic causes safety issues, %	33.23	25.22	25.97	0.18	0.16
Crime causes safety issues, %	11.75	9.02	6.18	0.10	0.18

Table 2: Covariate balance before and after pair matching. The mean in the treated group is Mean T, the mean of the control group before matching is Mean C Before, and the mean of the control group after matching is Mean C After. The standardized difference before matching is given by Standardized Difference Before, and the standardized difference after matching is given by Standardized Difference After.

The absolute values of all standardized differences after matching are less than 0.20, indicating acceptable balance.

4 Plan for Primary Analysis

The primary outcome of physical activity was measured by the survey question “In a typical week during the school year, how often does ^SCNAME exercise, play a sport, or participate in physical activity for at least 60 minutes a day? Would you say never, some days, most days, or every day.” We code this variable using the following scale, mapping each response to a number of days of a week: 0 = Never, 3 = Some days, 5 = Most days, 7 = Every day.

For the primary outcome, we fit a linear regression model including indicators for matched sets, and measure the effect of ADHD on physical activity with the estimated regression coefficient. To evaluate effect sizes for this outcome, we use the cutoffs described by [Cohen \(1988\)](#): 0.2 SDs for small effects, 0.5 SDs for medium effects, and 0.8 SDs for large effects.

The secondary outcome of sports participation was measured by the survey question “In the past 12 months, did ^SCNAME play or participate on a sports team or club or take sports lessons either at school or in the community?” We code this variable as 0 = No, 1 = Yes.

For the secondary outcome, we fit a conditional logistic regression and measure the effect of ADHD on sports participation with the odds ratio. As described by [Chen et al. \(2010\)](#), the cutoff for a small effect size is 1.5 and the cutoff for a large effect size is 5.0.

In addition to performing this analysis on the full sample, we will also perform two subgroup analyses, one stratified by sex and one stratified by age group (stratified by children (aged 6 – 12) and adolescents (aged 13 – 17)).

5 Sensitivity Analysis

Although controlling for observed baseline covariates through matching will reduce bias by balancing the distribution of observed confounders, it cannot guarantee the balance of unobserved confounders. Therefore, if we reject the null hypotheses of no treatment effect of ADHD on physical activity or sports participation, we wish to conduct a sensitivity analysis as described in [Rosenbaum \(2002\)](#) to determine the smallest amount of bias Γ that would alter our result. The value of Γ represents the amount of bias that would render our result insignificant; the larger the value of Γ , the stronger evidence there is for our causal conclusions. To perform the sensitivity analyses, we will use the `sensitivitymv` package in R for the continuous primary outcome, and the `binarysens` function of the `rbounds` package in R for the binary secondary outcome.

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